

SENTIMENTAL ANALYSIS IN COMPUTER LINGUISTICS

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Abstract. *The article describes the scientific views on the systematic approach to sentiment analysis and perceptual analysis of the text. The most common way to evaluate character weights in natural language processing (NLP) information retrieval is excused about TF and IDF frequency measure. The analysis of tonality in Uzbek linguistics which covered by the examples of adjectives, verbs and prepositions*

Keywords: *sentiment analysis, tonality, tonality measurement of text in TF, IDF, NLP, binary, multi-class, aspect analysis, tonality in loading.*

INTRODUCTION

The direction of analyzing and monitoring moods and attitudes expressed by people through text analysis is called sentiment analysis. In such an analysis, the attitude or emotions expressed in the text are automatically analyzed. In natural language processing, it is very important to divide them into emotional classes in order to determine the emotional sentiment of words. In this regard, a lot of systematic research has been done in Russian and English linguistics for pre-processing, vectorization and machine classification of certain text data.

LITERATURE AND METHODS

What is sentiment analysis? How is such an analysis conducted in world linguistics? What units should be used for sentiment analysis? What is the systematic approach to this topic? Which word groups should be classified as primary when expressing human emotions? In the article, we looked at theoretical knowledge about them.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In Uzbek linguistics, the scientific views of several scientists have been published on the topic of tonal analysis due to the researches being carried out on the subject of KL. Tonality analysis is divided into binary, multi-class and aspect-based types.

Binary analysis is analysis models that work only with positive and negative signs. This type of model assigns one of these two characteristics to the given text. For example: *I liked the movie because it was interesting* (positive); *The movie is very scary*. (negative)

Multi-class models are designed to work with more than two characters, in addition to positive and negative characters, neutral characters are also added. For example: *I liked the movie*. (positive); *I didn't like the movie*. (negative); *I saw the movie*. (neutral)

Aspect-based: This type of model divides a given text into many types based on its characteristics. In this, the aspects of the product or service being considered are taken into account, and the opinions expressed in this regard are clarified by the models. These aspects can range from the price of the product and service to its quality and convenience.

In the sentiment analysis of the text, the negative, positive and neutral relations between the object and the subject are automatically analyzed. The most common way to evaluate the weight of characters in information search is TF-IDF (see TF-term frequency IDF-inverse document frequency). This method is a statistical measure used to evaluate the importance of a word in the context of a document that is part of a set or corpus of documents. The weight of

certain words is proportional to the frequency of use of the word in the document and inversely proportional to the frequency of use of the word in all documents in the collection. The TF-IDF measure is often used in text analysis and information retrieval tasks, for example, as one of the criteria for matching a document to a search query, when calculating a document proximity measure during clustering.

In sentiment analysis -1.5 - 1.5 scale relationships are analyzed by keywords. An algorithm is developed by dividing the text into classes depending on the level of emotion from neutral to high, negative and high positive. In the logical network, all syntheses of the word network are automatically interpreted according to the concepts of "positivity", "negativity" and "neutrality". In Table 1, the negative-positive limit of the word is measured at -1.2 and +1.2

Table 1

-2	-1	0	+1	+2
Very bad	bad	dominant	good	The best
Bashara- face	Bet-face	Yuz-face	Chehra-face	Jamol-face

In verbs, this degree of tonal growth can go up to -1, -10 scale, maybe even more. For example, *to cry, to moan, to read, to squeeze, to grunt, to howl, to howl, to wail, to afghan, to faraj, to dod...*

TF (term frequency - word frequency) method is suitable only for one-way analysis of words. IDF (inverse document frequency) is the inversion of the frequency of occurrence of a certain word in the documents of the collection, that is, the inverse frequency of the document. The founder of this concept is Karen Spark Jones.

The primary keyword for building sentiment analysis binary models is quality. Adjectives define negative and positive tonality. **Pos:** *beautiful, beautiful, good, wonderful, beautiful, sweet, delicious, fragrant, pleasant...* **Neg:** *ugly, bad, unsightly, naughty, ugly, smelly, smelly...* Similarly, a vocabulary of positive and negative tonality helps sentiment analysis. The expression of tonality is also present in verbs, modal words and prepositions.

Different symbols and emoticons that express emotions on the computer are actually negative or positive expressions of human emotions. No serious research has been done on the sensation of downloads. For the first time, we tried to analyze the example of downloads. In the example of downloads, the emphasis itself is expressed in several ways. For example <*jonga tegdingku*> Strong emphasis <*Jonga tegding-da*> Medium emphasis <*Jonga tegding-u*> neutral emphasis. In these sentences, prepositions express negative tonality in three ways. <*Na ovchiman, va na botirman*> (A. Oripov) denial is strong. <*Ovchi ham, botir ham emasman*> low denial.

At a wedding (that is, at any wedding) At a wedding (even if you feed your belly) It is necessary to create scales that provide sentiment analysis to give two different meanings of the same syntactic structure when reading by a computer.

T. Nikolayeva evaluates the importance of prepositions in the speech process: "In order to fully understand the language, it is not enough to be able to speak it well, but also to be able to use the existing prepositions and modal words in the right place; skillful use of prepositions in speech is a sign of a rich knowledge of the language"

A. Shakhmatov was one of the first to give the interpretation of loading as an auxiliary word: "Loading is a group of words that strengthen or reduce the content of predicates or grammatical forms to one degree or another, and have a formal, auxiliary content". As Shakhmatov pointed out, the sentiment should be analyzed because the words that increase or decrease the

content of the downloads. Sentiment analysis subjective evaluation loadings *-jon, -oy, -bonu, -bek, -poshsho, -khan*, reinforcement-emphasis *-ku, -u(-yu), -da, -oq(-yoq), -ku, -kim, ham, axir, hatto, hattoki, naqadar, tim, g'irt, liq, jiqqa* discursive loadings are also expressed by *olgur, tushgur, tushmagur, gurgur*.

Adjectives that precede adjectives can also serve as a basis for sentiment analysis. Their expression of positive or negative tonality is determined by the meaning of the word to which it is added. For example, *very beautiful* (positive) *very ugly* (negative). Some of these downloads represent a negative tonality. They are loadings such as *girt, olgur, gurgur*.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be said that not all words in the language belong to the group of emotional lexemes. That is, not all words express human emotional relationships. Therefore, in Uzbek linguistics, as in Russian and Kazakh languages, words with positive and negative connotations are used to classify words emotionally. you need to create a dictionary. Sentiment analysis of Uzbek texts consists of passing the given text through the fundamental NLP (natural language processing) stage, for example, transliteration, tokenization, and then delivering it to the sentiment analysis model in the required format. Therefore, the creation of sentiment analysis models of the expressed thoughts in the given texts using technologies in the field of NLP is an urgent task for industry experts. Different symbols and emoticons that express emotions on the computer are actually negative or positive expressions of human emotions. But now Uzbek linguistics is waiting for serious research work to create programs that read the emotions of words.

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